

Eave tubes simple model

- t_1 average search time to locate a property
- t_2 average search time to locate a human host when searching indoors
- t_3 average time spent resting indoors post-feed
- t_4 average time spent finding ovipositing site
- t_5 average time spent from ovipositing to host searching
- t_6 cycles from infection to infectiousness
- μ_1 base mortality rate whilst searching for property or laying site
- μ_2 base mortality rate whilst searching for host inside property
- μ_3 base mortality whilst resting inside property (non IRS)
- μ_4 base mortality rate whilst outdoors and not searching
- P_1 proportion of properties with external protection (eave tubes)
- P_2 proportion of properties with eave tubes protected with IRS
- P_3 proportion of properties without ET which are protected with IRS
- P_4 proportion of ET properties protected with bednets
- P_5 proportion of people under bednets in ET properties with bednets
- P_6 proportion of non-ET properties protected with bednets
- P_7 proportion of people under bednets in non-ET properties with bednets
- P_8 probability per feed that mosquito will acquire Plasmodium infection
- P_9 probability that an entered ET property will have IRS
- P_{10} probability that an entered non-ET property will have IRS
- D_1 probability mosquito deflected away from ET-protected house
- D_2 probability deflected away from human under ITN
- D_3 probability exits ET property if deflected away from net-protected human
- D_4 probability exits non-ET property if deflected away from net-protected human
- D_5 probability deflected away from IRS protected property before selecting a host
- M_1 if not deflected, probability mosquito killed before entering ET protected house
- M_2 probability mosquito killed by ET/eave nets etc when exiting protected house
- M_3 if not deflected, prob mos. killed by bed net before feeds on human under net
- M_4 probability killed by bed net after feeding on human under net
- M_5 base mortality when attempting to feed - pre bite
- M_6 base mortality when attempting to feed - post bite
- M_7 base mortality when attempting to oviposit - pre lay
- M_8 base mortality when attempting to oviposit - post lay
- M_{10} probability killed by IRS whilst resting in IRS treated property

Probability survives search time to locate a property $S_1 = e^{-t_1\mu_1}$

Probability survives search to locate a human host indoors $S_4 = e^{-t_2\mu_2}$

Total probability deflected from located ET property without attempting to feed

$$D_6 = D_1 + (1 - D_1)(1 - M_1) \left(P_2 D_5 + (1 - P_2 D_5)(1 - M_2) \frac{P_4 P_5 S_4 D_2 D_3}{1 - S_4 P_5 D_2 (1 - D_3)} \right)$$

Total probability exits non-ET property without attempting to feed

$$D_7 = P_3 D_5 + (1 - P_3 D_5) P_6 \frac{S_4 P_7 D_2 D_4}{1 - S_4 P_7 D_2 (1 - D_4)}$$

Probability survives searching & enters a no-ET property $S_2 = S_1 (1 - P_1)(1 - P_3 D_5)$

Probability survives searching and enters an ET property $S_3 =$

$$S_1 P_1 (1 - D_1)(1 - P_2 D_5)(1 - M_1)$$

Probability survives background mortality whilst resting indoors $S_5 = e^{-t_3\mu_3}$

Probability survives background mortality whilst finding laying-site $S_6 =$

$$e^{-t_4\mu_4} (1 - M_7)$$

Probability survives background mortality between laying and host searching

$$S_7 = e^{-t_5\mu_4} (1 - M_8)$$

Probability survives & attempts to feed on human under bed net (in ET property)

$$S_8 = \frac{P_4 S_4 P_5 (1 - D_2)}{(1 - S_4 P_5 D_2 (1 - D_3))}$$

Probability survives & attempts to feed on human without bed net (in ET property)

$$S_9 = S_4 \left(1 - P_4 + \frac{P_4 (1 - P_5)}{1 - S_4 P_5 D_2 (1 - D_3)} \right)$$

Probability survives attacking to bite if feeding on bed-net protected human (in ET property) $S_{10} = (1 - M_3)(1 - M_5)$

Probability survives attacking to bite if feeding on human without bed net (in ET property) $S_{11} = 1 - M_5$

Probability survives feeding post-bite if feeding on bed-net protected human (in ET property) $S_{12} = (1 - M_4)(1 - M_6)$

Probability survives feeding post bite if feeding on human without bed net (in ET property) $S_{13} = 1 - M_6$

Probability survives indoor search and bites human under bed net (in ET property)

$$S_{14} = S_8 S_{10}$$

Probability survives indoor search and bites human without bed net (in ET property)

$$S_{15} = S_9 S_{11}$$

Probability survives locating and biting human under bed net (in ET property)

$$S_{16} = S_{14} S_{12}$$

Probability survives locating and biting human without bed net (in ET property)

$$S_{17} = S_{15} S_{13}$$

Probability vector in ET property is in IRS treated property

$$P_9 = \frac{P_2(1-D_5)}{P_2(1-D_5) + (1-P_2)}$$

Probability survives finding host, feeding, resting and exiting property in IRS treated property (in ET property) $S_{18} = (S_{16} + S_{17}) S_5 P_9 (1-M_{10})(1-M_2)$

Probability survives finding host, feeding, resting and exiting property in unsprayed property (in ET property) $S_{19} = (S_{16} + S_{17}) S_5 (1-P_9)(1-M_2)$

Probability survives & attempts to feed on human under bed net (in non-ET property)

$$S_{20} = \frac{S_4 P_6 P_7 (1-D_2)}{(1-S_4 P_7 D_2 (1-D_4))}$$

Probability survives & attempts to feed on human without bed net (in non-ET

property) $S_{21} = S_4 \left(1 - P_6 + \frac{P_6(1-P_7)}{1-S_4 P_7 D_2 (1-D_4)} \right)$

Probability survives attacking to bite if feeding on bed-net protected human (in non-ET property) $S_{22} = (1-M_3)(1-M_5)$

Probability survives attacking to bite if feeding on human without bed net (in non-ET property) $S_{23} = 1-M_5$

Probability survives feeding post-bite if feeding on bed-net protected human (in non-ET property) $S_{24} = (1-M_4)(1-M_6)$

Probability survives feeding post bite if feeding on human without bed net (in non-ET property) $S_{25} = 1-M_6$

Probability survives indoor search and bites human under bed net (in non-ET property) $S_{26} = S_{20} S_{22}$

Probability survives indoor search and bites human without bed net (in non-ET property) $S_{27} = S_{21} S_{23}$

Probability survives locating and biting human under bed net (in non-ET property)

$$S_{28} = S_{24} S_{26}$$

Probability survives locating and biting human without bed net (in non-ET property)

$$S_{29} = S_{25} S_{27}$$

Probability vector in ET property is in IRS treated property

$$P_{10} = \frac{P_3(1-D_5)}{P_3(1-D_5) + (1-P_3)}$$

Probability survives finding host, feeding, resting and exiting property in IRS treated property (in non-ET property) $S_{30} = (S_{28} + S_{29}) S_5 P_{10} (1-M_{10})$

Probability survives finding host, feeding, resting and exiting property in unsprayed property (in non-ET property) $S_{31} = (S_{28} + S_{29})S_5(1 - P_{10})$

Overall Probability per cycle mosquito survives to bite

$$S_{32} = \frac{S_3(S_{14} + S_{15}) + S_2(S_{26} + S_{27})}{(1 - S_1(D_6P_1 + (1 - P_1)D_7))}$$

Overall Probability per cycle mosquito survives to lay eggs

$$S_{33} = \frac{S_6(S_3(S_{18} + S_{19}) + S_2(S_{30} + S_{31}))}{1 - S_1(D_6P_1 + D_7(1 - P_1))}$$

Overall Probability mosquito survives full cycle $S_{34} = S_{33}S_7$

$$\text{Average infectious bites per vector per lifetime } LAIB = \frac{S_{32}P_8S_{34}^{t_6}}{(1 - S_{34})(1 - S_{34}(1 - P_8))}$$

$LAIB_0$ = average infectious bites per vector per lifetime with no intervention

Average infectious bites per vector per lifetime as proportion of value with no intervention $VLAIB = \frac{LAIB}{LAIB_0}$

The relative transmission potential (*RTP*) is defined as the average number of infectious bites per vector per lifetime per person expressed as a proportion of the number with no intervention

If we assume that juvenile density-dependence effects mean that the rate at which new adult vectors join the population is the same with and without intervention, and that the size of the human population is unaffected by any intervention, then $RTP = VLAIB$.

Average infectious bites per vector per lifetime per person for people using bednet in ET property

$$RTP_1 = RTP \times \frac{\text{proportion of bites per cycle taken on humans with ET \& net}}{\text{proportion of humans protected with ET \& net}}$$

$$= \frac{LAIB}{LAIB_0} \frac{S_3S_{14}}{S_3(S_{14} + S_{15}) + S_2(S_{26} + S_{27})} \frac{1}{P_1P_4P_5}$$

Average infectious bites per vector per lifetime per person for people not using bednet in ET property

$$RTP_2 = RTP \times \frac{\text{proportion of bites per cycle taken on humans with ET no net}}{\text{proportion of humans protected with ET \& no net}}$$

$$= \frac{LAIB}{LAIB_0} \frac{S_3 S_{15}}{S_3 (S_{14} + S_{15}) + S_2 (S_{26} + S_{27})} \frac{1}{P_1 (1 - P_4 P_5)}$$

Average infectious bites per vector per lifetime per person for people using a bednet in no ET property

$$RTP_3 = RTP \times \frac{\text{proportion of bites per cycle taken on humans with net \& no ET}}{\text{proportion of humans protected with net \& no ET}}$$

$$= \frac{LAIB}{LAIB_0} \frac{S_2 S_{26}}{S_3 (S_{14} + S_{15}) + S_2 (S_{26} + S_{27})} \frac{1}{(1 - P_1) P_6 P_7}$$

Average infectious bites per vector per lifetime per person for people not using bednet in no ET property

$$RTP_4 = RTP \times \frac{\text{proportion of bites per cycle taken on humans with no net \& no ET}}{\text{proportion of humans with no net \& no ET}}$$

$$= \frac{LAIB}{LAIB_0} \frac{S_2 S_{27}}{S_3 (S_{14} + S_{15}) + S_2 (S_{26} + S_{27})} \frac{1}{(1 - P_1) (1 - P_6 P_7)}$$